

Supplementary Material for “Structurally Restricted Fragments of Numeric Planning – a Complexity Analysis”

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This is supplementary material for the work Shleyfman, Gnad, and Jonsson (2023), and it has two parts. The first one contains the full proofs of Lemma 1 and Corollary 1 of section “Integer Restricted Tasks” of the main paper. The second part contains the complexity results that are only sketched at the end of section “Single Numeric Variable”.

Integer Restricted Tasks

We next show the correspondence of our integer form of RT to the original task. While, as previously mentioned, the transformation is very similar to the “domain simplification” of Helmert (2002), the correspondence to the original task has not been shown formally by Helmert (2002).

We define three conditions **P1** – **P3** for each $x \in \mathcal{V}_n$ as follows: **P1** holds if $\mathcal{C}_x \cup \mathcal{W}_x \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$, **P2** holds if $s_0[x] = 0$, and **P3** holds if $(x \in \llbracket l^-, l^+ \rrbracket) \in G_n$, then $l^-, l^+ \in \mathbb{N}_0$. We say that an RT $\bar{\Pi}$ is *integer* if conditions **P1** and **P2** hold. If **P3** holds, then we say that $\bar{\Pi}$ has a *bounded goal condition*.

Lemma 1. *Every plan for $\bar{\Pi}$ is also a plan for $(C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$ and vice-versa, where $C \in \mathbb{Q} \setminus \{0\}$ and $B \in \mathbb{Q}$.*

Proof. Let $\pi = \langle a_1, \dots, a_n \rangle$ be a plan for $\bar{\Pi}$. By s_k we denote the state that corresponds to the subsequent application of the first k actions of π , starting at the state s_0 . Suppose that $x \mapsto c_k$ is the effect of action a_k on x . Here we allow $c_k = 0$, so that each action has an effect on x . Thus, $s_k[x] = s_0[x] + \sum_{i=1}^k c_i$. Since each a_k is applicable in s_{k-1} , it holds that $s_{k-1}[x] = s_0[x] + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} c_i \in \llbracket a_k, b_k \rrbracket$, where $(x \in \llbracket a_k, b_k \rrbracket) \in \text{pre}(a_k)$, and $s_n[x] \in \llbracket a_g, b_g \rrbracket$, where $(x \in \llbracket a_g, b_g \rrbracket) \in G_n$. We need to show that π is also a plan for $(C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$. By induction, let s'_0 be the initial state of $(C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$, and suppose that π was applied to it up to some $k - 1$. Let s'_{k-1} be the resulting state. We need to show that $s'_{k-1} \models (x \in \llbracket C \cdot a_k + B, C \cdot b_k + B \rrbracket) \in \text{pre}(a_k)$. By induction we have that $s'_{k-1}[x] = C \cdot s_0[x] + B + C \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} c_i$. After some rearrangement we get $s'_{k-1}[x] = C(s_0[x] + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} c_i) + B \in \llbracket C \cdot a_k + B, C \cdot b_k + B \rrbracket$. The claim $s'_n \models G$ is proved exactly in the same fashion. Note that all other conditions and affects were left unchanged, and the map affects only the variable x , thus π is also a plan for $(C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$.

To prove the *vice-versa* part, i.e., any plan for $(C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$ is also a plan for $\bar{\Pi}$, we need to recall that if $C \neq 0$,

then the transformation $(C \cdot x + B)$ is invertible, i.e., $(C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$ is transformed into $\bar{\Pi}$ using the transformation $x \mapsto \frac{1}{C}x - \frac{B}{C}$. The claim follows by the previous paragraph. \square

Corollary 1. *For each RT $\bar{\Pi}$, there exists an integer RT $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ s.t. $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ is solvable iff $\bar{\Pi}$ is solvable. Moreover, $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ can be computed in polynomial time, $\|\bar{\bar{\Pi}}\| \in O(\|\bar{\Pi}\|^2)$, and the size of each number in $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ is at most $\|\bar{\Pi}\|$ bits.*

Proof. Consider the instance $\bar{\Pi}_x = (C \cdot x + B)(\bar{\Pi})$. If $C = \text{LCD}(\mathcal{C}_x \cup \mathcal{W}_x)$, then **P1** holds for x in $\bar{\Pi}_x$, and choosing $B = -C \cdot s_0[x]$ guarantees **P2**. By Lemma 1, $\bar{\Pi}_x$ is solvable iff $\bar{\Pi}$ is solvable. We finish by repeating this process for each $x \in \mathcal{V}_n$. This can be done since each map affects x independently of other numeric variables.

If $\|\bar{\Pi}\| = n$, then no number in $\bar{\Pi}$ uses more than n bits. Finding the least common multiple of a finite set $N \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ can be done in $\log_2(\max(N))$ steps, i.e., it is linear in the number of bits representing N . Thus, task $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ can be computed in polynomial time.

Let m_1 and m_2 be two numbers, then $\|m_1 \cdot m_2\| \leq \|m_1\| + \|m_2\|$ and $\text{LCD}(\{m_1, m_2\}) \leq \min\{m_1, m_2\}$, thus each number in $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ has at most n bits. Moreover, $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}$ has at most n numbers, each having at least one bit, so $\|\bar{\bar{\Pi}}\| = O(n^2)$. \square

Single Numeric Variable – Additional Results

Recall that an SNVT is an RT with a single numeric variable. We know that PESNVT is in **PSPACE** (Thm. 2). This can be refined into a pseudopolynomiality result:

Theorem A. *The problem PESNVT can be solved in pseudopolynomial time $O(\|\bar{\Pi}\|(4C_x^{\max} + M_x^+ - M_x^-))$.*

Proof. Let $\bar{\Pi}_x$ be an instance of PESNVT. Let $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}_x$ be the integer version of $\bar{\Pi}_x$. By Thm. 2, we can construct a bounded-interval SNVT $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}_x^I$ s.t. for each plan for $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}_x$ there is a plan for $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}_x^I$. By construction of the interval I we have that $|I \cap \mathbb{Z}| \leq 4C_x^{\max} + M_x^+ - M_x^-$. Note that x in the task $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}_x^I$ can take only integer values since $s_0[x] = 0$ and all additive constants are integers. Thus, to find a plan for $\bar{\bar{\Pi}}_x^I$ we can use dynamic programming, breaking down the problem into sub-problems of finding the shortest path from $x = 0$ to any of the integers in the interval I . Hence, the problem can be solved in time $O(\|\bar{\Pi}\|(4C_x^{\max} + M_x^+ - M_x^-))$. \square

If X is a set of SNVTs with bounded C_x^{\max} and $M_x^+ - M_x^-$, then the corresponding planning problem can be solved in polynomial time by Thm. A. We conclude this section by proving that if the parameters are not bounded, then PESNVT is indeed **NP**-hard.

Theorem B. PESNVT is *NP*-hard even if all preconditions are empty.

Proof. The basis for our proof is the feasibility version of the *change-making problem* (FEAS-CMP) (Martello and Toth 1990, Sec. 5). An instance is an n -vector (c_1, \dots, c_n) of non-negative integers and a non-negative integer b . The question is if there are non-negative integers x_1, \dots, x_n s.t. $\sum_{i=1}^n c_i \cdot x_i = b$? The **NP**-hardness of this problem was originally proved by Lueker (1975).

We present a polynomial time reduction from FEAS-CMP to PESNVT. Let (\bar{c}, b) denote an arbitrary instance of this problem with $\bar{c} = (c_1, \dots, c_n)$. We construct a planning task Π_x as follows: introduce a variable x and actions $a_i, i \in [n]$, with empty preconditions and effects $x += c_i$. The initial state is $x = 0$ and the goal state is $x = b$. The task Π_x can be constructed in polynomial time and (\bar{c}, b) has a solution iff Π_x is solvable. \square

References

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